

DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATION COMPETENCE OF MILITARY SERVANTS AS A SCIENTIFIC-PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM IN THE CONDITIONS OF INFORMING EDUCATION

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Abstract. *Working with information consists of the processes of collecting, processing and transmitting various data. This article analyzes the formation and development structure of military servants' communication competencies, effective use of information, as well as the competence of working with information in the conditions of education informatization.*

Keywords: *information, information competence, military personnel, communication, communication competencies, competency approach.*

The concept of information has various definitions in scientific literature and dictionaries. For example, information about objects, evidence, events and processes, knowledge and understanding about such objects, total evidence and information that may be of interest and should be stored and processed [17; p. 26], as well as "information" (lat. information - introduction, explanation) - a concept that has been used in philosophy since ancient times, and which later gained a new, broader meaning due to the development of cybernetics.

The term information is used in all aspects of human society, and based on them, the educational process is carried out and pedagogical activities are managed [2; p.32]. Information has gained a certain importance in the life of society, and in particular, it is considered the main source in the management of educational processes, because they are used to divide and process information received from the object into systems (partial systems) and to implement algorithms for transmission according to the desired goals. provides ample opportunities for implementation [2; p.30-31].

In the information space of the world civilization, every member of society uses information continuously in his daily activities [6; p.20]. That is, every member of society is an information consumer. The consumer of information needs information in order to satisfy his needs (increasing knowledge, education, etc.), the person and persons who seek and receive it [11; p. 30]. So, military personnel are also information consumers. At the same time, in the course of education, during daily activities, military personnel as an active consumer of information acquire the necessary information in the course of their educational activities. A number of scientific studies on education of information consumption culture of military personnel as consumers of information [16; p. 112] were conducted, in which special emphasis was placed on the functions of the culture of information consumption.

The scope of information use determines the level of development of society [3; p.27]. According to the conclusion of UNESCO, informatization is the wide application of means of collecting, storing and transmitting information. It provides systematization of existing knowledge and formation of new knowledge and their application for current management, further improvement and development [4; p. 12].

It continuously fulfills the task of forming and developing the skills of receiving and processing information of a military serviceman, and the increase in the level of assimilation of

information by students, the expansion of the scope of information use, serves to determine the effectiveness of education.

Work with information - collection, processing and transfer of various information [18; p.7] consists of processes. F.M. Kuchkarova's research works on the activation of the subconscious mechanisms of information processing in the student and the components of the development of evidence-based logical thinking [18; p. 7] emphasized the structuring and division of educational materials into blocks.

Understanding the content and essence of information is the basis of effective use of information. That is why it is important to form the concept of information in elementary school students. By understanding the content of information, interest in lessons and the desire to acquire new knowledge are maintained. [12; p. 224].

In many cases, military personnel understand the main content of the information, the meaning that is used in a wide range. Also, they are more attracted to the information that reflects the content of abstract concepts, imaginary events, and fictional images than the information that reflects the content of the real world around them. The main reason for this is that they do not understand the true nature of real events - events and objects. Military personnel cannot reflect them in their minds. For military servants, events that do not obey certain life laws and are fabricated by themselves or for them are more understandable. Therefore, it is important to familiarize with the basic content and secondary meaning of information .

It is important that military personnel understand the function that serves to ensure the communication process of information. The educational process is primarily a process of information exchange. The teacher provides relevant information to military personnel and in turn receives information that creates an idea of how the information presented in the form of feedback has been assimilated.

In fact, the basis of social development in the developing information flow society, along with traditional opportunities, are factors such as people's ability, initiative, creative approach to work, intellectual activity, independent improvement of their knowledge and skills [1; p.9].

Today's practice shows that it is necessary to constantly improve the issue of working with information in the educational process based on the requirements of the time. The demands of modern education are, in particular, "dynamic changes in the labor market, increasing demands for not only knowledge and skills, but also personal qualities of a person" [5; p. 17] created the need to organize education based on the competency approach, and several scientists studied the problems of education based on the competency approach and developed scientific and methodological foundations. According to M.M.Vahobov, "education based on a competency-based approach is education aimed at forming the competences of practical application of acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications in their personal professional and social activities" [5; p. 2].

Competency approach in education "... envisages teaching to effectively use competencies in various situations encountered in personal, professional and social life. Special attention is paid to the ability to use relevant knowledge, skills, and abilities when facing unexpected, uncertain, new, problematic situations. Therefore, in the process of teaching each subject, based on its content and characteristics, competences are formed for it" [10; p. 13].

State education based on the competency-based approach approved by the Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 187 dated April 6, 2017 "On approval of state education standards of general secondary and secondary special, vocational education" standard defines competence as "the ability to apply existing knowledge, skills and abilities in daily activities".

According to the analysis of scientific literature and dictionaries, the word "competence" derived from the Latin word "compyetyere" ("to be capable, worthy") means a person's awareness of a certain field, the level of knowledge of this field [10; p. 396].

The concept of "competence" was first mentioned in scientific literature in the 50s and 60s of the 20th century. American scientist N. Chomsky in his works entitled "Syntactic structures", "Aspects of the theory of syntax" interpreted competence as the ability of a person to perform an activity [11].

In the scientific literature, there are different views on the definition of the concepts of "competence" and "competent". F. Delamare and J. Winterton describe competence as standard behavior and behavior required by a certain activity, competence as the level of compliance with this requirement, that is, the final result of demonstrating competence [19; p. 28].

G.A.Asilova, summarizing the definitions of the concepts of "competence" and "competent", is the effective use of personal qualities and knowledge, skills and abilities in the process of working in a certain field; "competence" is an existing and possible ability to perform a certain activity [6; p. 12-13]

J.E.Usarov in his scientific work defines competence as "experience and knowledge in a certain field or direction, the manifestation of readiness to perform activities and the ability of a person to act successfully in various non-standard situations" [13; p. 22] showed the definition. According to B.Kh. Khodzhayev, "competence serves to integrate the student's self-development efforts to master new personal experience"[14; p. 101]. N.A. Muslimov [15] emphasizes that competence is not the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction.

Methods of diagnosing and correcting the formation of competencies in military personnel Yu. Asadov, N.Turdiyev, S.Akbarova, D.Tumirov's research works systematized and described the level of ability (competency) to apply the knowledge, skills, skills they acquired in life needs in the educational process aimed at the formation of competencies in military servicemen. effective tools and methods of diagnosis and correction are disclosed [1]. R.Fayzullayev [13; p. 9-11] conducted research aimed at solving problems related to the development of information competence in the educational process.

In defining the concept of competence, Safin expresses the difference between them without denying knowledge, skills and qualifications as follows: "the difference from knowledge is that competence exists in the form of activity, knowing only information about it (it is necessary to know, but it is capable of the practical aspect of knowledge is different from not being). The difference from qualification is that competence can change (be influenced by different objects) when solving different tasks. The difference from skills is that they are conscious and not automated, they allow a person to act not only in the usual environment, but also in a new unusual environment" [6; p. 69]. In her scientific works, N.F.Radionova emphasizes the nature of competence and the connection of human faith [9].

Today, when the content of education is being reformed in our country, the basis of the content of education is the formation and development of basic competencies in students. Basic competencies mean the ability to act independently in uncertain situations in solving problems considered relevant for the learner.

I.A. Zimnyaya distinguishes three main groups of basic competencies:

1. Self-related competence as a subject of a person's life and activity.
2. Competence of human interaction with other people.
3. Competence related to human activity. [9; p. 4-13].

In O.V.Temnyatkina's research work, emotional-psychological competence, regulatory (regular) competence, social competence, learning-cognitive competence, creative competence, self-development competence are considered as the basic competences formed in military servicemen during the educational process [12; 14-b] is shown. I.M. Pavlova believes that the place of computer information technologies is important in forming basic competencies of primary school students [9; p. 23].

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, based on the continuity and integrity of education, the priority of the individual and his interests, the following basic competencies are formed in accordance with their age characteristics.

Communicative competence;

Competence in working with information;

Self-development competence;

Socially active civic competence;

National and universal competence;

Mathematical literacy, awareness of scientific and technical innovations and competence in using [4; p. 139].

A number of scientific researches have been carried out on the issues of formation of competences for working with information. In the research works of G.S. Ergasheva, emphasis was placed on the development of information competence as a result of the gradual formation of skills for working with interactive software tools [13].

In her scientific research, N.A. Morozova emphasizes the need to form various basic competencies at different ages of personality development, in particular, the competence of working with information during the school period [8; p. 60-67]. According to V.V.Kyurshunova, the competence of a person to work with information is directly related to the process of informatization of society [7; p. 38]. In the research work, she emphasized that there are a number of competencies that must be formed throughout a person's life, and such competencies include the competence of working with information.

In the research work of O.B.Zayseva, the concept of "information competence" is interpreted as a complex individual-psychological education based on a defined set of personal qualities and the integration of theoretical knowledge and practical skills in the field of information technologies [6; p. 19]. In the scientific works of M.P. Lapchik, it was shown that knowledge in the field of information technology plays an important role in the development of the competence of working with information [6]. In addition, various definitions of the concept of competence in working with information have been given by scientific researchers. For example, O.G.Smolyaninova defines the competence of working with information as "the universal method of searching, receiving, processing, expressing and delivering information, summarizing, systematizing and turning information into knowledge" [11; p. 161] interprets as.

Structure of social experience:

Social activities, in particular, are mastered in the educational process and are formed as personal qualities, stabilize social relations.

Reflection structure:

It is manifested as individual characteristics with individual qualities, shows the directions of social activities.

Biological and physiological structure:

It combines biological characteristics of a person (for example, differences in the gender of learners) and physiological characteristics (age characteristics).

So, the competence approach in education appeared in connection with the preparation of military servicemen to be able to independently apply the acquired knowledge during life activities.

Core competencies based on analysis:

- has an integrative nature and implies the ability to apply the necessary knowledge during life activities as an integrative description of a person with social life;
- includes personal qualities as a comprehensive description of a person;
- competencies are manifested consciously and unconsciously during educational or life activities;
- subject-related competences, in turn, envisage the application of knowledge related to a certain subject in the fields of that subject;
- the results of the educational process are determined by the competencies formed and developed in military personnel;
- the competency approach serves to ensure unity of theory and practice in the educational process.

Based on the above-mentioned views of the authors and the collected materials, as well as the goals and tasks of the research, it was determined that theoretical knowledge and practical skills in the field of information technologies are also considered as competencies for working with information.

A number of scientific studies have been conducted on the use of information in the educational process, but the place and role of military personnel in the information field has not been sufficiently studied. After all, the main task of the educational process is to convey the necessary information to students, to achieve their assimilation, and to teach them how to use the acquired information.

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